

Research article

Micromagnetic study of grain junctions in MnAl-C containing intergranular inclusions

Markus Gusenbauer^{a,*}, Stefan Stanciu^a, Alexander Kovacs^a, Harald Oezelt^a, Johann Fischbacher^{a,c}, Panpan Zhao^b, Thomas George Woodcock^b, Thomas Schrefl^{a,c}

^a Department for Integrated Sensor Systems, University for Continuing Education Krems, 3500 Krems, Austria

^b Institute for Metallic Materials, Leibniz IFW Dresden, 01069 Dresden, Germany

^c Christian Doppler Laboratory for Magnet design through physics informed machine learning, 2700 Wiener Neustadt, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Triple junctions
Twin boundaries
Interface
Micromagnetic simulations
Carbide inclusions

ABSTRACT

In this work we quantify coercivity in single and multigrain systems of MnAl-C with embedded paramagnetic and soft magnetic inclusions. Soft magnetic inclusions with a diameter greater than 10 nm, where curling and multidomain reversal is triggered by adjacent hardmagnetic entities, led to only a fraction of the coercive field achieved without the inclusions. Large misorientation angles between the external field and the easy axes of participating structural units also led to low coercivity. This was frequently observed in triple junctions formed by twin boundaries, which is one of the reasons for the poor magnetic properties in as-transformed MnAl-C. After hot-extrusion, triple junctions formed by grain boundaries are dominant and the grains have an easy-axis texture parallel to the extrusion direction. Thus, large misorientation angles are minimized and coercivity is enhanced.

1. Introduction

Local demagnetization fields and exchange coupling between grains have a negative impact on the coercivity of permanent magnets. Interfaces in MnAl-C are known to have a major impact on the coercive field as well [1]. The appearance of crystallographic defects [2] and varying chemical segregation along the interfaces [3,4] are reasons for reduced coercivity as compared to the theoretical reachable nucleation field. Therefore the feasible usage of MnAl-C in hard magnetic applications is not yet given. Especially three types of twin boundaries, pseudo, true and order twins with different angles between respective entities easy axes, are located in as-transformed, die-upset as well as in hot-extruded MnAl-C [5]. True twins form during processing as a mechanism of relieving strain. Order and pseudo twins form during the phase transition from epsilon to tau. In as-transformed MnAl-C samples a large fraction of order and true twins can be found with a small fraction of pseudo twins. Due to symmetry reasons, pseudo twins necessarily appear at regions where order twins interact with true twins, which leads to triple junctions formed by twin boundaries. The grain size in as-transformed MnAl-C is in the range of several micrometers, which include many of the mentioned twin boundaries. After hot-extrusion, the grains are equi-axed with 0.5 to 1 micrometers and almost only true twin boundaries are left in the granular structure. There are also a few large non-recrystallized grains left, where a high

twin density is still present. Due to the lack of pseudo and order twins and the small granular microstructure, triple junctions present in hot-extruded samples are mainly formed by grain boundaries. Particularly at triple junctions formed by grain boundaries, carbide inclusions are frequently found [5]. In Fig. 1 we show a carbide inclusion next to grain boundaries and true twin boundaries resulting from the dynamic recrystallization of tau-phase grains during die-upsetting. During extrusion and the recrystallization of the grains the carbon dissolved in the lattice is tend to be pushed to the grain boundaries and other grain junctions. Especially at triple junction points, there is more free volume for precipitates to form.

Intergranular inclusions have been already investigated by micromagnetic simulations, as for example in Nd₂Fe₁₄B [6]. Here inclusions with reduced magnetocrystalline anisotropy in the intergranular regions lower the coercive field to comparable experimental values. The effect of carbide inclusions at triple junctions on the coercive field of MnAl-C have not yet been investigated.

We assume, that the properties of the carbide inclusions are soft magnetic, because of the cubic crystal structure and the multiplicity of easy axes [7]. Since the chemical composition of the carbide containing inclusions is not clear yet, the intrinsic magnetic properties are unknown. Therefore, we investigate two extreme cases, where

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: markus.gusenbauer@donau-uni.ac.at (M. Gusenbauer).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2024.172390>

Received 21 May 2024; Received in revised form 26 June 2024; Accepted 29 July 2024

Available online 31 July 2024

0304-8853/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Transmission electron microscopy image of carbide inclusion (A) in die-upset MnAl-C. True twin boundaries (red) with a twin angle of about 75° of adjacent easy axes and other grain boundaries (light gray) are observed next to the inclusion.

the inclusions are either paramagnetic or soft magnetic with a higher spontaneous magnetization and a lower anisotropy as compared to the main phase. In this work we calculate paramagnetic and soft magnetic inclusions, embedded in single and multigrain systems of MnAl-C, by micromagnetic simulations. As we are using these extreme cases, we expect the results to give a trend, rather than comparable values of real samples.

Similar to the missing intrinsic magnetic properties, we do not have the exact geometry of the inclusions. Therefore we apply extreme cases again, spheres and regular tetrahedrons, embedded in MnAl-C. The first accounts for an idealistic inclusion to investigate the impact of its intrinsic properties, whereas in the second the effect of sharp edges is included (compare Fig. 1). To understand the influence of soft magnetic inclusions at triple junctions we start with simple single grain geometries. Here the effect of the inclusion material and geometry can be analyzed without other effects like intergranular exchange. Then we place the inclusions at interfaces of two entities with different easy axes. In case of twin boundaries, this is located within a grain of MnAl-C. Here, the influence of misalignment of adjacent easy axes, the twin angle, is important. Later on we place the inclusions in the center of triple junctions, either formed by twin boundaries, typically found in as-transformed samples, or by grain boundaries, which are most prominent after hot-extrusion. Note, that for micromagnetic simulations, each entity with its own easy axis orientation, is handled individually. This can be a single grain or fractions of the grain separated by twin boundaries. Interfaces with spatial dependent magnetocrystalline anisotropy and exchange, as investigated by Zhao and co-workers [4], will not be investigated within this work. Also we had to limit the allowed angles and orientations for easy axes, external field, twin planes and misorientation between each of them to avoid an unmanageable number of simulations.

2. Methods

In the methods section we describe the simulation models we use to analyze extreme cases of carbide inclusions in MnAl-C, for single grains, twin boundaries and triple junctions. Simulations are performed with a high performance micromagnetic energy minimizer. Model geometries and easy axes configurations are acquired from scanning electron microscope and electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) imaging.

2.1. Interface and inclusion modeling

In this work we are interested in carbide inclusions at triple junctions of MnAl-C. To understand the effect of the inclusions on the resulting coercive field we start with a simple single grain model with

Fig. 2. Inclusion models of (a) single grain, (b) twin boundary and (c) triple junction. Inclusions are either spheres or regular tetrahedrons, paramagnetic or soft magnetic, with diameters ranging from 10 nm to 150 nm. Tetrahedrons have equivalent volume than the spheres and its center of mass lies exactly in the midpoint of the model. Tetrahedrons at twin boundaries (b) are slightly rotated to avoid numerical instabilities during meshing and simulation. The models contain 1, 2 and 4 entities with different easy axis orientation for (a), (b) and (c) respectively. Triple junctions are created with three lower entities and an additional upper half sphere.

Table 1

Material properties of MnAl-C [11] and soft magnetic phase [12], used for the bulk material and inclusion, respectively. Intrinsic magnetic properties: Saturation polarization $J_s = \mu_0 M_s$, magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant K and exchange stiffness constant A . The minimum of the Bloch parameter $\delta_0 = \sqrt{A/K}$ to resolve domain walls and the exchange length $l_{ex} = \sqrt{2\mu_0 A/J_s^2}$ to detect nucleation defines the minimum required mesh size [10]. Definition for coherence radius of ideal sphere $R_{coh}^{sph} \approx 2.5l_{ex}$ [9] which gives the transition length from coherent reversal to curling and multidomain reversal.

	J_s [T]	K [J/m ³]	A [J/m]	δ_0 [nm]	l_{ex} [nm]	R_{coh}^{sph} [nm]
MnAl-C	0.8	1.5×10^6	20×10^{-12}	3.65	8.86	22.16
soft magnetic phase	2.15	48×10^3	22×10^{-12}	21.41	3.46	8.65

centered inclusions (Fig. 2a). Then we analyze pseudo, true and order twin models (Fig. 2b). Later on we look at triple junctions formed by twin or grain boundaries (Fig. 2c).

To focus on the effects of interface properties with embedded inclusions we want to avoid demagnetizing effects arising from the shape of the model. Therefore, we use a spherical object consisting of one or several entities with different easy axis orientation. We use a model diameter of 500 nm to allow the formation and movement of domain walls and we add soft magnetic or paramagnetic inclusions in the center of the model. We expect nucleation to start at interfaces and at inclusions, which was confirmed by the simulations. Increasing the model does not provide qualitatively better values of coercivity and the computation would be unnecessarily long. An ideal magnetic particle follows certain modes of reversal depending on size and shape, such as coherent rotation, curling and multidomain reversal [8]. Abo et al. suggested to use $R_{crit} \approx 2.5l_{ex}$ to estimate the critical size for magnetization reversal by quasi-uniform rotation [9], which is 22.16 nm and 8.65 nm for MnAl-C and the soft magnetic phase, respectively (Table 1). In the simulations the magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant K and the orientation of easy axis of the soft magnetic phase has only a minor relevance to the resulting demagnetization curves, but K is important to estimate an accurate mesh size to resolve domain walls and to detect nucleation sites [10]. In the soft magnetic inclusions we apply an easy axis in z-direction throughout the work. A change of orientation did not alter the resulting demagnetization curves decisively. In a first step the inclusion is a sphere with a diameter ranging from 10 nm to 150 nm. Secondly we replace the sphere by a regular tetrahedron to model inclusions with sharp edges or corners (compare Fig. 1).

We require different angles to describe our simulation models (Fig. 3a). In this work we denote φ as the misorientation angle between the external field and an easy axis and ψ as the angle between the easy axes of two neighboring entities in the model.

In the twin model we use the coherent form without chemical segregation, hence the intrinsic magnetic properties do not change at the interface [4]. Twin boundaries are defined such, that the twin angle ψ between the easy axes of two entities connected via the twin plane is

Fig. 3. (a) Angular notation for the simulation models. φ represents the misorientation angle between external field and easy axis (ea) and ψ the twin angle between two adjacent easy axes. (b) Twin model entities as left and right hemisphere and symmetric easy axes around the twin plane. In real samples symmetric and asymmetric easy axes can occur [4]. Twin angle between the easy axes of the two entities is either ψ or $\psi' = 180^\circ - \psi$. (c) Geometry of lower half sphere of triple junction with exemplary 100 nm tetrahedral inclusion. The three twin or grain boundaries (dashed lines) meet at different angles.

about 48° (132°), 75° (105°) and 86° (94°) for pseudo, true and order twin, respectively [2]. As the easy axis has no direction, there are always two possible twin angles between neighboring entities (Fig. 3b). In this work we use the values of Zhao and co-workers [4] for the twin angles ψ . Due to numerical instabilities at twin boundaries during meshing, the tetrahedral inclusions are slightly rotated as depicted in Figs. 2b and 10. In our simulations the interface between the adjacent entities act as mirror plane, whereas in real samples this is not always the case. For instance, in the coherent form of a true twin boundary, there is a mirror plane, whereas in the incoherent form, the easy axes are not symmetric [4]. This can be measured by high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy and proofed by atomistic models. The reason for the different formation of the atomic structure, which occurs during the dynamic recrystallization of the tau-phase grains during die-upsetting or hot-extrusion, is not yet fully understood. We use symmetric easy axes for the twin model only to give a trend and to be able to compute the different settings in a reasonable time.

For triple junctions we firstly use EBSD measurements of as-transformed MnAl-C (Fig. 5) to obtain respective easy axes configurations. In this work we look closely at triple junctions A to D of the measurements. We set the crystallographic orientation of the EBSD data for the three entities at the lower half of the model (Fig. 2c). It is possible to use the same geometrical model for all triple junction configurations by just rotating the EBSD map around the z-axis, which points out-of-image. The external field is applied in z-axis, hence rotations do not alter the results. The upper half sphere of the model is a MnAl-C cap. Compared to the twin boundary model, the easy axes are not symmetric around the twin planes.

At first we look at triple junctions, where the individual entities are connected via twin boundaries. Later on we also analyze triple junctions formed by grain boundaries with special cases of misorientation angles φ between the external field and the respective easy axis. The angles, where the twin or grain boundaries meet at the center triple junction point, are usually 120° and in Fig. 3c, they take the values 125° , 140° and 95° . For simplicity we model the triple junctions from the cutting surface of the planar measurement and add a MnAl-C cap on top to complete the sphere. In real structures we do not always have a planar but arbitrary oriented interfaces as shown in Fig. 4.

Note, that due to the slight rotation of tetrahedral inclusions at the twin model and the different meeting angles that form the triple junctions, the inclusion volume is not equally distributed among the part-taking entities. A rotation of the tetrahedral inclusions cause a change of overall geometry as well and thus alter the results.

2.2. Micromagnetic simulations

We create a finite element mesh of the described models with the pre- and postprocessing software Salome (salome-platform.org, last visited on 31/10/2023). The 500 nm model sphere, which includes the

Fig. 4. Approximation of a granular structure created with the polycrystal generator and mesher Neper [13]. Spherical model excerpt on 2-dimensional surface (blue center point) and inside the 3-dimensional structure (yellow center point). Black grain boundary edges meet at the center triple junction point.

inclusion, is placed in a much larger sphere ($5 \mu\text{m}$). In such a way, boundary conditions for computing the magnetostatic potential, can be treated at infinity [10]. The mesh size of the base model is set to the smallest characteristic length scale of MnAl-C and the soft magnetic phase. The characteristic length scale is defined such, that domain walls can be resolved accurately [14]. In Table 1 we list intrinsic magnetic properties and the minimum required mesh size for MnAl-C and the soft magnetic phase. The mesh size of the base model is set to 3 nm and mesh size of the surrounding air is gradually increasing from 3 nm to 30 nm. We tested also a finer mesh size for the 10 nm inclusions to resolve possible domains, yet results did not alter decisively. The number of finite elements is varying from about 40 to 50 million elements for the different described models within this work.

We compute demagnetization curves of the above described models of single grain, twin boundaries and triple junctions with embedded soft magnetic inclusions, to obtain and compare coercive field values. The coercive field in this work is defined as the field, which is required to demagnetize a saturated magnet to $\mu_0 M = 0$ T. Due to the relatively large amount of finite elements we compute the demagnetization curves with a time-independent micromagnetic solver. The solver runs on graphical processing units (GPUs) and minimizes the Gibbs free energy, which is the sum of exchange, anisotropy, demagnetization and external field energy [15]. We gradually reduce the external field $\mu_0 H_{\text{ext}}$ from 10 T to -10 T in steps of 0.01 T. For the case with the external field H_{ext} aligned in z-direction we usually apply a slight rotation by 1° to avoid numerical instabilities.

2.3. Experimental measurements

In previous studies we investigated atomistic structures and chemical composition of true and order twin boundaries in MnAl-C using aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy coupled with electron energy-loss spectroscopy [4]. For this study we embed soft magnetic inclusions at the interface and we use the data for coherent true and order twin models. Large scale microstructural images are obtained by emission gun scanning electron microscope in combination with EBSD. Crystallographic orientation information for each entity is used to color interfaces according to the twin angle ψ between adjacent easy axes (Fig. 5). Data for the pseudo twin configuration is obtained from previous EBSD studies [2]. The carbide inclusion in Fig. 1 is obtained by bright field transmission electron microscopy and is formed during the die-upsetting process as a result of

Fig. 5. Electron backscattered diffraction data of MnAl-C with sample size of $180 \mu\text{m} \times 81 \mu\text{m}$. The color code visualizes twin boundaries with different twin angle ψ between respective easy axes and other grain boundaries in gray. Positions A to D indicate triple junctions of interest. Note, that the grain boundary in B is only slightly above the 2° limit of the pseudo twin range.

the dynamic recrystallization of the tau-phase grains. As the recrystallized grains grow, solute carbon is rejected to the growth front, where it accumulates. The carbide phase forms when the concentration of carbon is sufficiently high.

3. Results and discussion

In the following we analyze the demagnetization curves of the models with paramagnetic and soft magnetic inclusions embedded in single grains, at twin boundaries and in the center of triple junctions. Our simulations showed that the orientation of the weak anisotropy in soft magnetic inclusions does not have a significant effect on the demagnetization curves. Consequently, this aspect is not further addressed in this paper.

3.1. Single grains with inclusions

The Stoner–Wohlfarth (SW) switching field for ideal single domain ferromagnets [16] is calculated by

$$H_{\text{SW}} = (2K/J_s) \left(\cos(\varphi)^{2/3} + \sin(\varphi)^{2/3} \right)^{-3/2} \quad (1)$$

Taking the intrinsic magnetic properties K and J_s of MnAl-C in Table 1 and the misorientation angle φ from 0° to 90° between the external field and the easy axis we obtain a typical Stoner–Wohlfarth curve in Fig. 6 on the bottom right.

In Fig. 6 we show coercive field H_c with increasing inclusion size. We compare an aligned case with misorientation $\varphi = 15^\circ$ between external field and easy axis. H_c of spherical and tetrahedral inclusions is about the same for paramagnetic inclusions and decrease slightly with inclusion size. A large reduction of H_c is caused by soft magnetic inclusions greater than 10 nm. Here tetrahedral inclusions show a bit weaker performance than spherical ones.

An ideal MnAl-C single domain ferromagnet has a nucleation field $\mu_0 H_{\text{SW}} = 4.71$ T. In our simulations we have to rotate the external field slightly away from the z -axis by 1° to avoid numerical instabilities. This reduces $\mu_0 H_{\text{SW}}$ to 4.27 T, which is in good agreement with the single grain model without an inclusion. A larger misorientation $\varphi = 15^\circ$ of the main bodies easy axis to the external field follows the Stoner–Wohlfarth curve and reduces $\mu_0 H_c$ by more than 1 T. This is always true for paramagnetic inclusions regardless of their size. The effect of misorientation vanishes at soft magnetic inclusions greater than 10 nm because coercivity values are about the same for the aligned case and the misorientation $\varphi = 15^\circ$.

Nucleation for both inclusion geometries starts cylindrically inside the soft magnetic phase and prolongs to the inclusion surface until the whole grain switches in a single step. Nucleation inside the 150 nm soft magnetic inclusion is visualized in Fig. 6 on the right.

Fig. 6. On the left: Coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ as function of inclusion size for a single grain. On the right: Nucleation starts from the center of the soft magnetic inclusions, which is shown for both 150 nm inclusion geometries. On the bottom right: Stoner–Wohlfarth switching field $\mu_0 H_{\text{SW}}$ as function of misorientation angle φ between the external field and the easy axis of a single domain ferromagnet [16] with material properties of MnAl-C (Table 1).

In brief, single grains without an inclusion always perform better, than those with. Models with paramagnetic inclusions show higher H_c than with soft magnetic inclusions but drop with misorientation φ according to the Stoner–Wohlfarth theory (Fig. 6 on the bottom right). For up to 10 nm soft magnetic inclusions misorientation described by the Stoner–Wohlfarth theory is dominant, yet for larger soft magnetic inclusions the difference between aligned and misorientated models vanish. Here, early nucleation inside the inclusions determines H_c (Fig. 6 on the right).

3.2. Twin boundaries with inclusions

Three types of twin boundaries are investigated by splitting the spherical model in half and assigning the respective easy axes (Figs. 2b and 3b). The twin angles $\psi = 48^\circ$ [2], $\psi = 75.66^\circ, 95.35^\circ$ [4] between the two easy axes are set for pseudo, true and order twin boundaries, respectively. We introduce the same inclusions as in the single grain study, i.e., spherical or tetrahedral, paramagnetic or soft magnetic, with sizes ranging from 10 nm to 150 nm. The external field is applied in z -direction and rotated by 15° into the right hemisphere.

In Fig. 7 we show resulting coercive fields H_c with increasing inclusion size for pseudo, true and order twin boundaries. The twin models without an inclusion show a reduced H_c compared to the Stoner–Wohlfarth switching field H_{SW} for single domain ferromagnets. $\mu_0 H_{\text{SW}} = 2.59$ T, 2.38 T, 2.36 T for each of the half spheres, compared to $\mu_0 H_c = 2.44$ T, 2.16 T, 1.74 T, for the pseudo, true and order twin model with aligned external field, respectively. The reduction is much larger in the order twin model. The reason for the drop of H_c in the twin models can be explained by exchange and magnetostatic interactions of the two neighboring entities. With increasing twin angle, coercivity of the paramagnetic inclusions as well as small soft magnetic inclusions are decreasing. This follows the results of [17,18], where large enclosed twin angles ψ between two neighboring easy axes have a negative effect on H_c . The coercive field of the samples with paramagnetic inclusions does not change with the size of the inclusion. In all cases tetrahedral inclusions have a more deleterious effect on the magnetic properties than do spherical inclusions. Note, that rotating the tetrahedral inclusions can alter this effect, which is examined in the next section.

In Fig. 8 we show demagnetization curves for pseudo, true and order twin models with soft magnetic inclusions. We compare the external field aligned with the z -axis and rotated by 15° into the right

Fig. 7. Coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ as function of inclusion size for pseudo, true and order twin configurations. The blue curves refer to the samples with paramagnetic inclusions. The red curves refer to samples with soft magnetic inclusions. Twin angle ψ between the two easy axes, $\psi = 48^\circ$, $\psi = 75.66^\circ$ and $\psi = 95.35^\circ$ for pseudo [2], true and order twin [4], respectively.

Fig. 8. Demagnetization curves with soft magnetic inclusions for pseudo, true and order twin boundaries with an external field aligned and rotated by 15° into the right hemisphere. Twin models are stacked horizontally and different alignments of the external field vertically.

hemisphere. Note, that rotating the external field leads to different H_{SW} values for the left and right hemisphere, because the misorientation angle φ between the external field and the respective hemisphere easy axis is either smaller or larger. The corresponding H_{SW} values for the right and left hemisphere are $\mu_0 H_{SW} = 3.25$ T, 2.37 T for pseudo twins, $\mu_0 H_{SW} = 2.62$ T, 2.39 T for true twins and $\mu_0 H_{SW} = 2.43$ T, 2.52 T for order twins. Pseudo twin boundaries with the small enclosed twin angle ψ between the easy axes switch in a single step independent of the orientation of the external field. True twin boundaries with an aligned external field switch in a single step as well, with an exception of 150 nm tetrahedrons. Order twin boundaries show a 2-step progression from 50 nm inclusions upwards. Yet with rotating the external field into the right hemisphere the progression of the curves transforms from a single step to a thin 2-step switch for true twins, and from a 2-step to a much broader 2-step switch for order twins. The 2nd step in the demagnetization curve originates from (1) a larger twin angle ψ between the two easy axes, (2) the size and/or the geometry of the soft magnetic inclusion, and (3) a rotation of the external field

into one hemisphere. Interesting curls in the soft magnetic core can be observed (see magnetization states of the 100 nm spherical soft magnetic inclusion of order twin model, Fig. 9). In the reversible part of the demagnetization curve a curly nucleation inside the soft magnetic core starts. At some point an increase of the external field leads to an irreversible switch of the left hemisphere and later on to a full demagnetization of the whole model. Note, that the magnetization of the MnAl-C hemispheres rotate preferably in plane of the two easy axes whereas the soft magnetic inclusion can rotate in all directions.

3.3. Rotation of inclusions at twin boundaries

Note, that with rotated tetrahedral inclusions, the resulting curves change, as we change the geometry of the simulation model decisively. For demonstration we use the order twin model, we keep the geometry the same, and apply the external field once in z-direction and compare it with an external field applied in y-direction (Fig. 10). In the small

Fig. 9. Magnetization arrows and domain wall inside the 100 nm soft magnetic inclusion of order twin model with aligned external field. From left to right: (1) initial saturation prior nucleation, (2) curly nucleation inside the soft magnetic core, (3) domain wall moves towards inclusion boundary, (4) domain wall breaks down, (5) left hemisphere switches, (6) full demagnetization.

Fig. 10. On the left: Coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ as function of inclusion size for an order twin with an external field H_{ext} applied in z and y direction. In the center: Tetrahedral inclusions pointing in out-of-image z and y direction with corresponding easy axes configurations. On the right: Demagnetization curves of the soft magnetic inclusions.

inlets of Fig. 10 we show the tetrahedral inclusions split by the twin plane, pointing into out-of-image z and y plane. A slight rotation of the tetrahedrons in the z-axis causes an unequal volume fraction lie in the left and right hemisphere of the twin model. In order to achieve the same orientation relation between the external field and the easy axes, we have both easy axes in the x-z plane for the field applied along the z-axis and the easy axis in the x-y plane, for the field applied along the y-axis.

Coercivity H_c remains constant for all sizes of paramagnetic inclusions. Due to the symmetry of spherical soft magnetic inclusions, a change of external field direction has no influence on resulting H_c . But with tetrahedral soft magnetic inclusions greater than 50 nm H_c is decreasing with the external field applied in y direction. Demagnetization curves in Fig. 10 on the right show, that with large tetrahedral inclusions and $H_{ext,y}$ the first irreversible step is occurring earlier, whereas the second step follows after the steps of $H_{ext,z}$.

It is important to note, that inclusion material, geometry and size alters resulting coercivity values. Without inclusions or with very small inclusions of 10 nm, the effect of those three parameters is negligible. But with larger inclusions, where curling and multidomain switching occurs, all of the three parameters need to analyzed carefully and individually.

3.4. Twin boundary triple junctions with inclusion

In this section we are analyzing triple junction configurations, where three different twin boundaries meet. In MnAl-C this can be frequently seen in the as-transformed state. In Fig. 5 A to D the triple junctions of interest are highlighted, from which the easy axis information is obtained for the model. The external field is applied in z-direction and the capping half sphere (see Fig. 2c) is aligned with the external field.

In Fig. 11 on the left we show coercive field H_c with increasing inclusion size for all four triple junctions. Despite different easy axis configuration the trend is similar. Without inclusions the coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ ranges from 1.4 T to 2.05 T. These values are far below the single grains in Section 3.1, yet compared to twin boundaries in

Section 3.2 the resulting values are in a similar range. Here again exchange and magnetostatic interactions between the individual entities reduce H_c compared to H_{SW} . Similar to all other models in this work, paramagnetic inclusions have only little effect on resulting H_c despite inclusion size and soft magnetic inclusions greater than 10 nm drastically reduce H_c . Spherical inclusions always perform better than tetrahedral inclusions. A rotation of the capping half sphere easy axis by 15° out of the z-axis can slightly reduce or enhance coercivity, but shows the same trend.

A deeper understanding of the switching behavior of triple junctions is obtained by the nucleation sites. For paramagnetic inclusions nucleation starts at the entity with the largest misorientation from easy axis to external field ($\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$) to the smallest one ($\varphi \rightarrow 0^\circ$), yet the irreversible switch is always happening at once in a single step. Usually the triple junctions with the soft magnetic inclusions switch in a single step too, yet with large soft magnetic inclusions minor steps in the 3rd quadrant of the demagnetization curve can occur (see demagnetization curves for triple junction C in Fig. 11 on the right). In triple junctions A, B and D all entities switch simultaneously for all inclusion configurations. In triple junction C inclusions with 100 nm and greater show a 2-step switch and even a 3-step switch. For the 2-step curves the capping half sphere plus the two entities most parallel to the external field switch first. And finally the entity with $\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$ fully demagnetizes the model. In the 3-step case, the capping half sphere switches first and afterwards the two entities most parallel to the external field. Due to the strong demagnetization field of the already switched entities, the last one with $\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$ switches last.

In a triple junction configuration based by twin boundaries, one of the entities is very likely misorientated perpendicular to the external field ($\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$). This is caused by the strict symmetry at regions where pseudo, true and order twins interact. The larger the soft magnetic inclusion, the earlier nucleation begins in these highly misorientated grains (see extract of triple junction C in Fig. 11 on the right). And with increasing volume of reversed magnetization, a full demagnetization of the model is accelerated.

Fig. 11. On the left: Coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ as function of inclusion size for triple junctions A to D of Fig. 5. Easy axis configurations without inclusion are shown as inlay with out-of-image z-direction. The capping half sphere easy axis is aligned with the external field in z-direction. On the right: Demagnetization curves for triple junction C with soft magnetic inclusions. Early nucleation of the entity with $\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$ and the 150 nm spherical soft magnetic inclusion is shown for C prior the first irreversible step.

3.5. Grain boundary triple junctions with inclusion

After hot extrusion of as-transformed MnAl-C samples the grain size distribution is drastically reduced by at least a factor of 10 and the appearance of twin boundaries is now dominated by true twins [2]. Thus, triple junctions formed by twin boundaries, occur very rarely. On the other side, triple junctions formed by grain boundaries, especially with an enclosed inclusion, are frequently seen (Fig. 1) [5]. The grains easy axes in hot extruded samples tend to be more favorably orientated in the extrusion direction, which increases the remanence [2].

From previous studies we know that a large twin angle ψ between adjacent easy axes is disadvantageous for coercivity, as seen for MnAl-C [18] and in general for hard magnetic materials [17]. Further on we have a maximum reduction of coercivity by a misorientation angle $\varphi = 45^\circ$ between the external field and a grains easy axis, which is described by the Stoner–Wohlfarth theory (Fig. 6 on the bottom right). Due to the numerous possibilities of grain boundary triple junction configurations we are focusing on three easy axes misorientations from the external field applied in z-direction, $\varphi = 15^\circ, 45^\circ, 75^\circ$. On the x–y plane the easy axes are equally distributed around 360° (0° lying on the x-axis, 120° and 240° , compare small inset on the top right in Fig. 12).

In Fig. 12 we compare different easy axes configurations. There is a clear reduction of coercivity when all three entities forming the triple junctions have an increase in the misorientation angle φ . For paramagnetic inclusions coercivity is close to 3T, 2T and 1T for $\varphi = 15^\circ, 45^\circ, 75^\circ$, respectively. Again with soft magnetic inclusions a drastic reduction of H_c can be observed after 10 nm, but still a smaller φ shows better performance than larger ones. Tilting only one of the three easy axes to $\varphi = 45^\circ$ or $\varphi = 75^\circ$, and keeping the others at $\varphi = 15^\circ$, shows a reduction of coercivity for paramagnetic inclusions for all inclusion sizes. Here again, the larger φ the worse H_c . With soft magnetic inclusions greater than 10 nm the trend is similar to the model with equal φ . Adding another easy axis that is tilted by 45° or 75° further reduces coercivity with the same trend as before. Interestingly,

the configuration with all three entities tilted by 45° shows slightly better performance, compared to only two entities tilted by 45° . The comparison of 75° tilts show that a single entity tilted by 75° shows the best performance, followed by two and later on by all three entities tilted by 75° .

All easy axis configurations having only 15° and 45° tilts show single step switching in the demagnetization curves (not shown in this study). As soon as one entity is tilted by 75° , a very small step can be observed in the 3rd quadrant of the hysteresis curve (compare Fig. 11 on the right). Having two easy axes with $\varphi = 75^\circ$ leads to a 3-step switch. And all of them tilted by 75° show even a 4-step switch. Thus each entity forming the triple junction and the capping half sphere switches individually.

We expected the configuration with $\varphi = 45^\circ$ to have the lowest coercivity, as we know from the Stoner–Wohlfarth theory for single domain ferromagnets (compare Fig. 6 on the bottom right). In our model with multiple entities we have additional exchange and magnetostatic interactions which lowers coercivity especially with $\varphi = 75^\circ$. Here twin angles ψ between the easy axes are unfavorably large as we know from previous studies of MnAl-C [18] or other hard magnetic materials [17]. The results also confirm the findings from twin boundary triple junctions in the previous section.

4. Summary

Junctions between both grains and twin boundaries, containing inclusions of different geometries (spheres and regular tetrahedrons) and magnetic properties (paramagnetic and soft magnetic with low magnetocrystalline anisotropy) were modeled and the magnetic properties were studied using micromagnetic simulations. A 500 nm sphere of MnAl-C has an ideal nucleation field of 4.71 T. If we have a separating interface, in which the easy axis of both entities are misorientated to the external field, the switching field is reduced. This is typical for

Fig. 12. Coercive field $\mu_0 H_c$ as function of inclusion size for triple junctions formed by grain boundaries. The easy axis of the upper half sphere is aligned with the external field applied in z-direction. On the top right a schematic of the easy axis configuration is depicted with the misorientation angles $\varphi = 45^\circ, 45^\circ, 45^\circ$ between the external field and the easy axes. On the x-y plane the easy axes are equally distributed around 360° .

twin boundaries. For one hemisphere of the twin model the Stoner–Wohlfarth switching field is 2.59 T, 2.38 T and 2.36 T for pseudo, true and order twins, respectively. Whereas including the exchange and magnetostatic interactions between both entities, early nucleation is favored and the switching field is reduced to 2.44 T, 2.16 T and 1.74 T, respectively. According to [17], magnetostatic interactions of coupled grains reduce the ideal nucleation field by 10%, whereas exchange coupling by about 40%. Including paramagnetic inclusions in the center of the 500 nm sphere has only a minor effect at single grains and almost no effect at twins or triple junctions. Up to 10 nm the soft magnetic inclusions have no influence at twin or triple junctions as well. The geometry of the inclusions and its influence on coercivity get dominant with diameters greater than 10 nm. Here, coherent rotation inside soft magnetic inclusions transforms to curling and multidomain reversal. This leads to a drastic reduction of coercivity. The effect of misorientation of the easy axes to the external field gets less prominent with soft magnetic inclusions greater than 50 nm. The increase in overall soft magnetic content in the model elevates saturation magnetization, a faster reduction of the magnetization in the reversible part of the demagnetization curve can be observed and multiple independent switching steps are possible. Due to the specific easy axis configuration at triple junctions, a large misorientation angle $\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$ between external field and easy axis of one or more entities, favors a drastic reduction of coercivity. In triple junctions formed by twin boundaries, this is almost always the case. Thus also further explains the low bulk coercivity for as-transformed MnAl-C with many twin boundary triple junctions with respect to hot-extruded MnAl-C, where mostly grain boundary triple junctions are found with easy axes more or less aligned in extrusion direction.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Markus Gusenbauer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Stefan Stanciu:** Investigation, Data curation. **Alexander Kovacs:** Conceptualization, Visualization. **Harald Oezelt:** Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Johann Fischbacher:** Software, Validation. **Panpan Zhao:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Thomas George Woodcock:** Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Thomas Schrefl:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded in whole or in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) I 5266-N, the German Research Foundation (DFG) 326646134 and the Gesellschaft für Forschungsförderung NÖ, as part of the RTI-Strategy Lower Austria 2027, FTI22-D-009.

References

- [1] S. Bance, F. Bittner, T.G. Woodcock, L. Schultz, T. Schrefl, Role of twin and anti-phase defects in MnAl permanent magnets, *Acta Mater.* 131 (2017) 48–56.
- [2] F. Bittner, L. Schultz, T.G. Woodcock, Twin-like defects in L10 ordered τ -MnAl-C studied by EBSD, *Acta Mater.* 101 (2015) 48–54.
- [3] D. Palanisamy, D. Raabe, B. Gault, Elemental segregation to twin boundaries in a MnAl ferromagnetic Heusler alloy, *Scr. Mater.* 155 (2018) 144–148.
- [4] P. Zhao, M. Gusenbauer, H. Oezelt, D. Wolf, T. Gemming, T. Schrefl, K. Nielsch, T.G. Woodcock, Nanoscale chemical segregation to twin interfaces in τ -MnAl-C and resulting effects on the magnetic properties, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 134 (2023) 22–32.
- [5] P. Zhao, L. Feng, K. Nielsch, T.G. Woodcock, Microstructural defects in hot deformed and as-transformed τ -MnAl-C, *J. Alloys Compd.* 852 (2021) 156998.
- [6] J. Fidler, T. Schrefl, S. Sasaki, D. Suess, The role of intergranular regions in sintered Nd-Fe-B magnets with $(BH)_{max} > 420$ kJ/m³ (52.5 MGOe), in: *Proceedings of XI Int. Symposium on Magnetic Anisotropy and Coercivity in Rare Earth Transition Metal Alloys*, Sendai, Japan, 2000.
- [7] X.-Y. Wang, P.-Z. Si, H.-D. Qian, Y. Yang, H.-L. Ge, J. Park, X.-Q. Wang, C.-J. Choi, The effect of Mn/Al substitution on the structural stability and magnetic properties of Mn₃AlC, *J. Magn.* 24 (1) (2019) 123–127.
- [8] J.M. Coey, *Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [9] G.S. Abo, Y.-K. Hong, J. Park, J. Lee, W. Lee, B.-C. Choi, Definition of magnetic exchange length, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* 49 (8) (2013) 4937–4939.
- [10] J. Fischbacher, A. Kovacs, M. Gusenbauer, H. Oezelt, L. Exl, S. Bance, T. Schrefl, Micromagnetics of rare-earth efficient permanent magnets, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 51 (19) (2018) 193002.
- [11] J. Thielsch, F. Bittner, T.G. Woodcock, Magnetization reversal processes in hot-extruded τ -MnAl-C, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 426 (2017) 25–31.
- [12] L. Exl, D. Suess, T. Schrefl, *Micromagnetism*, *Handb. Magnet. Magn. Mater.* (2020) 1–44.

- [13] R. Quey, P. Dawson, F. Barbe, Large-scale 3D random polycrystals for the finite element method: Generation, meshing and remeshing, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Engrg.* 200 (17–20) (2011) 1729–1745.
- [14] M. Gusenbauer, J. Fischbacher, A. Kovacs, H. Oezelt, S. Bance, P. Zhao, T.G. Woodcock, T. Schrefl, Automated meshing of electron backscatter diffraction data and application to finite element micromagnetics, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 486 (2019) 165256.
- [15] J. Fischbacher, A. Kovacs, H. Oezelt, T. Schrefl, L. Exl, J. Fidler, D. Suess, N. Sakuma, M. Yano, A. Kato, et al., Nonlinear conjugate gradient methods in micromagnetics, *AIP Adv.* 7 (4) (2017).
- [16] E.C. Stoner, E. Wohlfarth, A mechanism of magnetic hysteresis in heterogeneous alloys, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. A. Math. Phys. Sci.* 240 (826) (1948) 599–642.
- [17] T. Schrefl, H. Schmidts, J. Fidler, H. Kronmüller, The role of exchange and dipolar coupling at grain boundaries in hard magnetic materials, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 124 (3) (1993) 251–261.
- [18] M. Gusenbauer, H. Oezelt, J. Fischbacher, A. Kovacs, P. Zhao, T.G. Woodcock, T. Schrefl, Extracting local nucleation fields in permanent magnets using machine learning, *npj Comput. Mater.* 6 (1) (2020) 1–10.